

Measurement of color and chemical composition changes in natural gemstones by optical photometry and X ray fluorescence (XRF) before and after thermal treatments in air

Livio Rosai

retired physicist, Arese, Italy¹

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1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of this work

The aim of this work is to show how color variations in gemstones samples of natural sapphire, topaz, aquamarine, zircon, amethyst and emerald caused by heat treatments can be measured objectively (i.e. quantitatively) by transmission optical spectrometry. The composition and the presence of impurities and inclusions inside them, including those responsible for giving the color, have been determined by the XRF technique. This work is confined to the case of heating treatments at temperatures in the range 250-700 °C, in oxidizing atmosphere .

1.2 What produces colors in gemstones (for the benefit of not experts in the field) [1]

The colors displayed by the gemstones are due to the presence (inclusions) of certain transition metals such as Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu. or some rare earth metals, having partially filled (unpaired) 3d-shells, called 'color centers'. Under certain circumstances the color center can be non-transition-element impurity ions or a crystal defect such as a missing ion. The combination of these impurities and defects within the crystal structure creates unstable species, absorbing visible photons of light which are re-emitted in other regions of visible spectrum.

The natural color of **ruby** is due to chromium replacing aluminum in the crystal structure. Chromium is also responsible for the green color of **emerald**. The blue color of natural **sapphire** results from electron transfer of traces of iron (Fe^{2+}) and titanium (Ti^{4+}) ions replacing aluminum ions (Al^{3+}) in the crystal structure. Most natural **topaz** is colorless, but it can also be pale yellow, pink, orange, brown, blue, green or gray. The pink and reddish hues result from chromium, manganese, iron and titanium, substitution for aluminum. Iron introduces yellow, orange, and brown tones, depending on concentration; chromium creates pink, red, and violet-to-purple hues; manganese can contribute to pink and reddish tones. The pale blue color of **aquamarine** is attributed to Fe^{2+} . The Fe^{3+} ions produce a golden-yellow color, and when both Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} are present, the color is a darker blue. The tetravalent cations Hf, U, and Th and rare earth elements are also common in **zircon**. In the **amethyst** trace amounts of iron (Fe^{3+}) are present within the quartz crystal lattice. These iron atoms replace some of the silicon atoms in the quartz structure. Over millions of years, the surrounding rocks of the amethyst have emitted natural radiation. This radiation caused changes in the oxidation state of the iron atoms, creating the purple hue.

¹ e-mail: livio.rosai@alice.it

1.3 Brief resumé of thermal heating effect in gemstones [2] [3]

It is common practice to submit various types of gemstones such as corundum (ruby, sapphire), topaz, aquamarine, amethyst, tourmaline, zircon, to irradiation (X rays, gamma rays, alpha, beta particles, neutron bombardment) as well as to heat treatments, oiling, or other processes to improve appearance.

These processes can be carried out alone or in combination among them in order to enhance the gemstones color, clarity and visual appeal. The fundamental idea behind heat treatment is to repeat in short times the natural long geological processes that occurred deep within the Earth's crust.

When a specific wavelength band (for example around 450 nm, in the blue region) of the incoming light spectrum carries enough energy to raise an unpaired electron in 3d-shell to a higher energy state, the energy of this wavelength is completely absorbed by the electron transition. This means that this particular wavelength (or color) is removed from the spectrum, or better "absorbed".² However if the energy transferred to the color center is significantly higher than the exciting energy, as in the case of heating the gemstone, at sufficiently high temperature the electron will not return to the ground state but will jump out and escape, thus destroying the color center.

One of the primary goals of heating gemstones is to intensify or modify their color. By carefully controlling the heating process, undesirable colors can be minimized or eliminated, leading to a more vivid and attractive appearance. In addition, the heat treatment can reduce or remove internal and surface inclusions, improving the gem's clarity. Finally, this process sometimes makes the stone more transparent and visually appealing to consumers and collectors. The final result is that of increasing the market value of gemstones with enhanced colors or clarity. In addition to oxygen atmosphere, as in this paper, many heat treatments of gemstones are carried out under reducing atmosphere which allows color transformation not obtainable in oxygen atmosphere. The final color, structure integrity and appearance are strictly dependent from various parameters such as temperature, heating and cooling time. Heat treatment of gemstones is a delicate process: improper conditions can lead to various damages. In particular both the slopes of raising temperature and cooling must be very gentle to avoid cracks.

In more detail, the effect of heat treatment in causing changes of colors or variation of luster is due to following different mechanisms:

- oxidation of low-valence cations to a higher valence state (for example F^{2+} to Fe^{3+}) or vice versa in reducing atmosphere, thus creating or destroying color centers.
- repairing crystal structural damage or defects, for instance in **topaz** reducing the yellow component, and turning the gemstone pink or, as in **aquamarine**, minimizing impurities that cause the green, leaving behind a pure, crystal pastel blue. Heat treatment can enhance the clarity of **emeralds** by reducing or removing inclusions, which are impurities within the stone that can affect its appearance.
- diffusing impurities (chromogenic ions). These ions, due to heating for sufficient time, can migrate uniformly across the gemstone until occupy a lattice site or fall into a lattice defect. In this position they become active centers in changing the color. The heat induced diffusion is also adopted for doping the gemstone with substances capable of causing color changes, added in form of powders

² The light energy is usually transformed to heat when the electron falls down to its original (ground) state.

surrounding it inside the furnace during the heating process. Mostly chromium-oxide (Cr_2O_3), titanium-oxide (TiO_2) or iron-oxide (Fe_2O_3) powder is used.

-changing or modifying deliberately the lattice structure of the gemstone, as for example in zircon when heated above 1000°C . The high temperature causes the atoms and molecules within the stone to vibrate and move more quickly leading to changes the crystal lattice structure of the gemstone.

-release of gases and other impurities trapped within the stone, which can impact its clarity and color.

The main chemical compositions, crystal structure, typical impurities and inclusions and corresponding colors of some of the most popular gemstones, are reported in Table I. In the same table a summary of literature data on temperature and duration of heat treatments and their typical effect in changing color of the gemstone are reported. The data of the table are only indicative because the sources reported in literature are limited and somewhat inconsistent. In addition, similar thermal treatments on gemstones of same natural color but of different geographical origin can result on different colors.

2. Instruments and methods

The characteristics of gemstone before and after treatments can be identified with various instrumental methods, the most important of which are: microscopic examination, to analyze the internal features of the sample such as healed fractures or alterations in the crystal structure and spectroscopic analysis of absorption spectra to analyze uniformity and distribution of color. In addition, gemologists may employ testing techniques such as fiber optics visible photo spectrometry, ultraviolet light fluorescence, X-ray diffraction, XRF (X ray fluorescence), UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy, or even laser ablation ICP-MS to obtain detailed information about a gemstone's composition and treatment history. For the scope of this work the XRF and the fiber optical visible spectrometry have been employed.

2.1 How to objectively compare the change of color of gemstone due to thermal (or radiative) treatments

Nowadays there are in commerce relatively inexpensive portable spectrophotometers capable of reading and automatically display and compare by reflectance the colors of objects (including gemstones) by simply contacting them with the reading window.

It could however be interesting to understand the scientific principles on which such devices are based. To this aim the physics basis governing the measurement of colors are first summarized.

In this work, the instrumental color attribution to the gemstones samples was done by transmittance by using a simple laboratory layout combined with the optical spectra obtained with a portable spectrometer that measures the light intensity transmitted by a (transparent) sample as a function of wavelengths in the visible spectrum, displaying the results as a chart of intensity vs. wavelength in the spectrometer software.

The spectrometer uses light in the visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum and just into the near infrared (from 400 nm to 800 nm).

Figure 1 – Data Harvest optical spectrometer connected to the fiberoptics cable

By using the fiber optical cable of which the instrument is equipped the spectrometer is able to detect the color output of transparent colored samples, acting as light filters, such as gemstones, illuminated by a light source.³ The instrument is shown in figure 1.

In order to obtain results comparable with those of illumination with natural light it is necessary that the light source be as much as possible close to the natural black body radiation (even if with a different color temperature).

The light source used for this work was that of a torch with a xenon lamp at 3500 K. In order to avoid that part of the beam of light reached the spectrometer without crossing the gemstone, the experimental apparatus shown in figure 2 has been adopted.

Figure 2– Drawing of the experimental layout

In figures 3 and 4 respectively, the optical spectrum of the natural sunlight and that of the 3500 nm xenon are shown. As it can be seen all the wavelengths of the natural light are present in the spectrum of the xenon lamp. This is the reason why the xenon lamp is the most common system employed in Sun simulators.

³ The spectrometer was manufactured by Data Harvest Ltd

Figure 3 – Optical spectrum of natural sunlight

Figure 4 – Optical spectrum of the 3500 K lamp used for the tests

Mathematically speaking the spectrum is a function $P(\lambda)$ which gives, for any wavelength λ in the human visual range of 400 through 750 nanometers (nm), the intensity emitted (per small constant-width wavelength interval centered about λ), normally in units of watts per nm or counts.

The curves in figure 5 show the relative contributions of spectrum wavelengths to the mean human eye tristimulus values. Using these curves, it is possible to reproduce the color (“color matching”) corresponding to a particular spectrum measured by an instrument.

To do that the so called “CIE⁴ color matching functions X, Y, Z are adopted [4]. These coordinates are calculated over the visual range, by summing the products of the intensity and wavelengths small intervals as follows:

$$(1) \quad X = \Delta\lambda \sum_{400}^{750} x(\lambda)P(\lambda) \quad Y = \Delta\lambda \sum_{400}^{750} y(\lambda)P(\lambda) \quad Z = \Delta\lambda \sum_{400}^{750} z(\lambda)P(\lambda)$$

⁴ CIE: International Illumination Commission Digitare l'equazione qui.

Figure 5 -Tristimulus curves of the spectral response of human vision

Here x , y , z are the intensity values in the red, green and blue regions of the spectrum. As it can be seen in figure 5, the regions of red, green and blue stimulus are partially overlapping. Thus, in the overlapping zones the intensity measured by the instrument must be attributed in the right percentage. This is done by the expressions in (1).

The above X , Y , Z values are then normalized in x , y , z coordinates to be inserted in the CIE diagram of figure 6.⁵ using the expression (2). Here x , y , z have nothing to do with the same letters in italics as in (1) :

$$(2) \quad x = \frac{X}{X+Y+Z} ; \quad y = \frac{Y}{X+Y+Z} ; \quad z = \frac{Z}{X+Y+Z}$$

With this normalization: $z = 1-x-y$, allowing to use only two coordinates (x,y) in the CIE diagram.

Simple on-line free of charge programs can be used for calculate the x,y coordinates in the CIE diagram starting from the optical spectra, and see the corresponding color, indicated with a point in the diagram of figure 6. It is not possible to compare directly the absolute intensities of the spectrum of the sample illuminated by xenon lamp before and after thermal treatments, because the sensitivity of the apparatus varies significantly among different measurements even for small alignment differences. However, the ratios of the intensities vs wavelengths are not affected by the variations of the sensitivity of the apparatus, so that the normalization in the expressions (2) overcomes this difficulty. For the same reason (at least with the apparatus used in this work) it is not possible to measure the variations in transparency of the samples before and after the thermal treatments. For most applications sampling wavelength bands 5 or 10 nm apart is adequate.

⁵ The point corresponding to specific values of x and y are defined **Color temperature**. This is a parameter describing the color of a visible light source by comparing it to the color of light emitted by an idealized opaque, non-reflective body. The temperature of the ideal emitter that matches the color most closely is defined as the color temperature of the original visible light source.

As an example, the expressions (1) and (2) have been used to calculate, with an on-line free Internet program [5], the color temperature corresponding to the spectrum of the xenon lamp of figure 6. The calculated coordinates are: $x=0.3823$, $y=0.40$ and the corresponding point of color temperature in the CIE diagram is shown in figure 6⁶.

This work is confined in measuring the x , y coordinates of samples. In addition of reading the x , y values, modern spectrophotometers can read other important parameters such as luminosity, reflectance and opacity.

Figure 6 – CIE chromaticity diagram with indication of coordinates of light emitted by the xenon lamp.

2.2 The XRF technique

The XRF (X-ray Fluorescence) is a simple, non-contact, non-destructive, not invasive analysis technique that is ideal for use in precious materials testing [6],[7],[8],[9],[10]. This technique is useful in quantifying the elements (composition) that occur in many gem materials, as well impurities and inclusions that are evidence of certain treatment processes. It is also useful in discriminating gems of different origin, natural and synthetic. The portability of hand held XRF spectrometers such as that used for this study is especially useful when used for analysis of mounted gemstones such as rings, brooches, necklace brooches. The use of this technique is occasionally reported in gemstones literature although it is not a common tool as it would deserve, probably because of the not negligible cost of the apparatus.

⁶ These values correspond to a color temperature of 4099 K, slightly higher than the theoretical color temperature of the lamp (3500), due to the intrinsic limitations of the experimental apparatus

The XRF spectrophotometry allows to know, in real time, the composition of a sample through the emission of x ray fluorescence radiation. The availability, now for over thirty-five years, of portable versions equipped with software capable of data processing and showing the analysis on the instrument display or by downloading them to an associated PC, allows a wide range of applications [6]. The fluorescence is the property of some substances to re-emit (in most cases with longer wavelength and therefore less energy) the electromagnetic radiation received. In particular this is the case when the incident radiation and the reissued radiation belong to the x-ray spectrum. The basic mechanism is as follows: when the incident beam is characterized by appropriate energy and intensity, it is possible to create, for photoelectric effect, a vacancy in an inner shell of the atom of a given element. The system thus goes in an imbalanced condition, which can be re-established when another electron with less energy replaces the vacancy, freeing up a photon that therefore has an energy equal to the difference between the electron energies in the two initial and final positions. The x-fluorescence radiation emitted by a chemical element has a characteristic spectrum which depend on their energy. The x-ray fluorescence energies are tabulated for all elements which make them in principle recognizable and distinguishable from any other element. The x-ray energies generally used (dozens of keV) involve almost exclusively the electrons of the inner K, L, M shells, so the chemical bonds are not altered.

It must be remembered that the examination of the characteristic x-ray fluorescence emitted by atoms identifies with great confidence the individual chemical elements but not the compositions, if they are in the form of compounds. There are essentially two limitations to the XRF technique: (a) due to their low fluorescence energy, it is difficult to detect elements with energies below about 2 Kev, such as lithium, beryllium, sodium, boron, carbon and oxygen, and of course elements whose fluorescence energy is above the energy of photons of primary x radiation; (b) the x-rays penetration increases with their primary energy and decreases with the density of the sample material in a range from a few microns to a few hundred microns. This translates into practice in the fact that XRF technology is only applicable for analyzing thin surface layers of the sample.

A modern XRF equipment consists of the following main components: a miniaturized x-ray generator tube, a solid-state detection system of fluorescence radiation (generally silicon-lithium), an electronic system that transforms analog signals into digital and sorts them according to their energy through a multichannel analyzer. The signals are sent to a computer for processing the data in form of an x-ray fluorescence spectrum which, by showing the number of counts as a function of energy, makes it possible to recognize rather easily the peaks characteristic of each element. The data are shows on the display of the instrument, in form of spectra or directly in terms of the percentage of concentration of the individual element, with a confidence coefficient of more than 95%. The instrument can be equipped with different measuring modes, according to the type of samples to be analyzed: 'Soil', 'Mining' and 'General Metals'.

The instrument used in this study was the NITON model XL2 980 GOLDD spectrometer manufactured by the leading USA company *Thermo Fisher Analytics*.⁷ In fig 7a and 7b the block scheme of the instrument and an actual picture of it are shown. The abovementioned XRF model is one of the most advanced versions of the series, capable of detecting light elements such as magnesium, silicon, aluminum (the latter two very important in analysis of gemstones composition) and precious metals.

⁷ Represented in Italy by *Sirio Analytics* Srl of Lodi (Milan)

The figure 8 shows the actual pictures of the samples before and after the thermal treatments reported in table II.

3.1 Compositions before and after thermal treatments

As expected, due to the modest market price of the samples procured for this study, in addition to the elements reported in table I, responsible for giving the color to the gemstone, in the samples number 3,6,7 there are several other impurities, each contributing between 0.01 to 0.1 per cent in weight. The only exception are Calcium (4.1%) and Magnesium (1.09%) in brown zircon. The small changes of compositions after thermal treatments might be due to intrinsic variations of composition between different points of the sample surface explored by collimated the x-ray beam rather than effect of the treatment: the latter can only cause changes of oxidation status or diffusion of the metallic elements but not variations of their quantity.

It must be mentioned that in the sample No 2, the orange -brown topaz, the values of aluminum and the balance read by the XRF spectrometer are quite incorrect due the picks overlapping because crystal matrix reflection effects. The same happens to the readings of composition and the balance in the brown zircon. More in general the regular crystalline nature of the samples might have caused some imprecisions of the readings. These difficulties could be overcome adding a dedicate software to the XRF instrument.

In addition, in appearance, the composition of abovementioned sample No2 is lacking of elements such as Cr-Fe-Mn-Ti and that of sample No 3 (zircon) is lacking of elements such as Hf, U, Th (Nb is present) that, according to Table I, should responsible of giving the color to these gemstones. In reality some of such elements could be present in the samples and contribute in creating the colors albeit below the low detection limit of the XRF analyzer (generally between 0.01 and 0.01 ppm).

3.2 Effects of thermal treatments on color changes

a) sample 1- emerald green topaz:

in spite of a prolonged heating at 500 °C for 20 hours only a marginal change of color was observed, towards a slightly blue tint.

b) sample 2 -orange brown topaz:

according with literature [15] a moderate heating at 320 °C for short time (30') was sufficient to make the sample almost transparent.

c) sample 3- brown zircon:

the sample was heated in steps from 340 to 600 °C for a total of almost 8 hours. The final color was pale brown, in agreement with literature that explains the effect of heating to recrystallization [20].

d) sample 4 – pink sapphire:

as reported in Table I significant changes in color with most sapphires need heating temperatures between 800 and 1800 °C, not reachable with the furnace available for the tests. Only a modest color change (removal of subtle blue tint) can be obtained on the pink sapphire if heated in the range of 400-800 °C, that is the case of this work with a thermal treatment at 650 °C for 4 hours.

e) sample 5 -amethyst:

the heating of the sample in steps from 280 to 510 °C for a total of about 6 hours has produced the expected significant color change [21] from purple to citrine.

d) sample 6 -aquamarine:

the thermal treatment at 475 °C for over 12 hours has produced a discrete change of color from quasi-transparent to an opaquer greenish blue. Tests repeated with other aquamarine samples up to 675 °C did not produce the significant deep blue tint claimed in literature [19], possibly because the different origins of the samples (Brasil in this case, Vietnam in the literature's reference) and/or the absence of Fe³⁺ in addition to Fe²⁺.

e) sample 7 – emerald:

in the gemstone industry it is well known that heat treatments of emeralds at high temperatures, aiming to produce more vibrant and green colors, followed by rapid cooling, are susceptible to cracking or shattering of the gem. The sample used in this work was heated at 670 °C for 2 hours and 20 minutes and cooled naturally in the furnace, causing a more agreeable green tint but also a complete fragmentation of the sample.

Figure 8- Pictures of the samples before and after the thermal treatments

4. Conclusions

Samples of some of the most popular natural gemstones: sapphire, topaz, aquamarine, zircon, amethyst and emerald have been submitted to thermal treatments similar to those reported in literature, in the range 250-700 °C, in oxidizing atmosphere. The variations of colors induced by the treatments have been quantitatively measured by transmission optical spectrometry according to the CIE color matching functions. The composition of the samples and the presence of those impurities responsible of giving the colors (among others) has been determined by the XRF technique. In particular, significant color changes induced by the heating treatment have been observed on topaz, amethyst and emerald.

Table I – Composition, crystal structure and typical impurities of some of the most popular gemstones and relative common thermal treatments (*)

Gemstone and main composition	Crystal structure	Typical impurities/ inclusions/ crystal defects (**)	Color of natural not irradiated gem	Heat treatment in air: temperature/ duration in literature	Typical effect of heat treatment in air
<p>Topaz [15] [16] $\text{Al}_2\text{SiO}_4\text{F}_x(\text{OH})_{(2-x)}$ $x \geq 0 \leq 2$</p>	<p>orthorhombic; dipyramidal</p>	<p>Combination of impurities (Fe, Cr, Mn, Ti) and defects within its crystal structure creating an unstable species absorbing visible photons of light re-emitted in other regions of visible spectrum</p>	<p>all colors</p> <p>brownish yellow</p> <p>brown/orange</p> <p>yellow-brown</p> <p>yellow-reddish brown</p> <p>yellow-green</p> <p>blue</p> <p>green/violet</p>	<p>1000 °C, duration unknown, probably hours</p> <p>From 300 to 400 °C for 3 hours</p> <p>500°C for minutes to hours</p> <p>200-400°C for a few hours 200-300°C for a few minutes (other source)</p> <p>400-500°C</p> <p>400°C for minutes to hours</p> <p>450 °C for minutes or hours 500°C (duration unknown (other source))</p> <p>treatment unknown</p>	<p>colorless</p> <p>dark red-brown</p> <p>pink</p> <p>bleached</p> <p>bleached</p> <p>colorless</p> <p>brown</p> <p>bleached</p> <p>blue</p>

Zircon [20] ZrSiO₄	cubic	Traces of Hf- U-Th-Nb- rare hearts	colorless		
			reddish brown	from 200 to 500 (duration unknown)	light brownish orange
			reddish brown	600°C (duration unknown)	pale brown
			yellow, orange, red, green pink, blue hues	900°C (duration unknown)	golden yellow to colorless
Sapphire [11] [12] [13] Al₂O₃ (corundum)	Rhomb- hedral (generally treated as a hexagonal)	no inclusions	colorless	700-800 °C duration unknown	Slight shift of color
		(Fe3+) - (Ti3+)	pale blue	from 800 to 1200 °C for 8 hours from 1200 to 1500°C (time unknown)	some discoloration more vibrant and uniform color/color deepens to dark blue
		(Fe3+) - (Ti4+)	dark blue	1700°C for 20 hours 1800 °C for 4 hours	lightening the blue reducing the blue patch
		(Fe3+)	yellow	1800 °C for 3 hours or days (other source)	reducing color zoning, intensifies yellow and more vibrant color
		(Fe3+) –(Fe2+)- (Cr3+)	green	from 1300 °C to 1600 °C for 40 h	yellow
		(Cr3+)	pink	400-800°C for 2 hours	removes subtle blue tint
		(Cr3+)- (Fe2+) –(Ti4+)	purple	no data	
		V(3+)	violet	no data	
		(Cr3+) - (Fe2+) + sometimes (V3+)	orange	no data	

Ruby [14] Al₂O₃ (corundum)	hexagonal	(Cr 3+) up to 1%	red	From 1300 °C to 1600 °C for 24 hours	intensifies red color and transparency
Amethyst [21] SiO₂	hexagonal	(Fe4+)- (Fe3+)	Three phases of color change: purple stage ≤ 350 °C, lighter stage between 370 °C and 480 °C, and light yellow ≥ 480 °C	From 350 to 560°C, duration unknown	citrine
Aquamarine [17] [18] [19] Be₃Al₂(SiO₃)₆	hexagonal	(Fe2+)- (Fe3+)	greenish blue	250-400 °C up to 12 hours 700 °C, duration unknown (other source)	blue
Emerald [22] Be₃Al₂(SiO₃)₆	hexagonal	Cr3+-V3+	yellow-green to blue-green	In general, none. If done not above 600°C (avoid cracks)	more vibrant green color
Diamond C	cubic	N-S-B-Ni-crystal lattice distortions	colorless, yellow-brown, pink, blue, green, black, red orange	None	

(*) There are several common gem materials not addressed in this article such as spinel, tourmaline, turquoise and others

(**) Traces of several other elements such as Mg, Si can be present

Table II – Type of gemstones studied, heat treatments, chemical compositions and coordinates on CIE diagram before and after heating

Sample n. Gemstone type/ origin	Carats	Max/min dimensions (mm)	Heating temperature and duration	CIE color coordinates		Theoretical composition in case of zero impurities (in weight%)	Composition (in weight %)		Color coordinates (x, y) before and after thermal treatment on chromaticity diagram
				Before thermal treatment	After thermal treatment		Before thermal treatment	After thermal treatment	
1 Emerald green Topaz	6.61	Ø 10	500 °C for 20 h	X 0.327 Y 0.421	X 0.314 Y 0.419	Al 29.3 -30 Si 15.2-16.6 Bal (H+F+O) 54.4 -55.4	Al 28 Co 0.342 K 0.179 Si 10.64 Bal 60.74	Al 29.57 Co 0.358 K 0.042 Si 11.13 Bal 58.88	
2-Orange brown Topaz /unknown	31.81	21.6x16x9.7	320 °C for 30'	X 0.382 Y 0.396	X 0.346 Y 0.37	Al 29.3 -30 Si 15.2-16.6 Bal (H+F+O) 54.4 -55.4	Al 16.5 Ba 0.011 Si 10.42 K 0.035 Balance (O-F-H) 73.6	Al 17.7 Ba 0.091 Si 10.42 K 0.035 Balance (O-F-H) 71.77	
3- Brown Zircon/ Cambogia	27.3	17x13x7,2	340 °C for 2 h, then to 520 °C for 3 h, then to 600 °C for 2 h 40'	X 0.454 Y 0.418	X 0.346 Y 0.37	Si 15.2 Zr 49.8 Bal (O) 35	Al 0.257 As 0.012 Ba 0.341 Ca 4.1 Co 0.024 Cr 0.059 Cu 0.25 Mg 1.09 Nb 3.76 Ni 0.229 Si 14.87 Zr 68.04 Bal. 6.83	Al 0.296 As 0.013 Ba 0.345 Ca 3.2 Cr 0.06 Cu 0.24 Mg 0.433 Nb 4.05 Ni 0.243 Si 15.92 Zr 71.32 Bal. 6.9	
4- Pink Sapphire/ unknown.	20.25	15x12x9	650 °C for 4 h	X 0.41 Y 0.274	X 0.395 Y 0.278	Al 53 Bal (O) 47	Al 49.31 Si 0.018 Ba 0.013 Cr 0.106 Bal. 50.44	Al 54.82 Si 0.025 Ba 0.012 Cr 0.113 Bal. 45.01	

5-Amethyst/ unknown	4.36	10x11x6.4	280 °C for 2h 45, then for 3h 30' to 510 °C	0.369 0.367	0.39 0.44	Si 46.7 Bal 53.3	Fe 0.04 Ca 0.03 K 0.509 Si 53.15 Bal. 42.29	Fe 0.03 Ca 0.03 Mg 0.0309 Si 49.16 Bal. 50.52	
6 - Aquamarine/ Brasil	6.20	Ø 10	475 °C for 12h 15'	0.373 0.429	0.352 0.431	Al 10.21 Si 31.86 Bal (Be+O) 57.92	Al 9.14 Fe 0.575 K 0.142 Mg 0.213 Nb 0.011 S 0.069 Si 32.68 Ti 0.039 Zn 0.034 Bal. 57.09	Al 8.49 Fe 0.585 K 0.262 Mg 0.228 Nb 0.014 S 0 Si 31.43 Ti 0 Zn 0.035 Bal. 58.96	
7-Emerald/ Columbia	40.6	17x17x9,2	670 °C for 2h 20'	0.216 0.615	0.323 0.493	Al 10.21 Si 31.86 Bal (Be+O) 57.92	Al 10.11 Ag 0.019 As 0.014 Ba 0.407 Ca 0.1 Cd 0.038 Cl 0.479 Cr 0.035 Cu 0.169 K 0.178 Mn 0.033 Ni 0.03 P 0.773 Se 0.119 Si 31.71 Sn 0.04 Ti 0.308 V 0.216 Bal .55.61	Al 9.86 Ca 0.145 Cd 0.042 Cl 0.460 Cr 0.037 Cu 0.243 K 0.145 Mn 0.03 Ni 0.025 P 0.786 Se 0.121 Si 31.71 Sn 0.028 Ti 0.291 V 0.190 Bal. 56.95	

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